

Customers' Perception of Gold Loan Scheme- A Comparative Study of Banking and Non Banking Financial Companies

Ninikala K

Guest Lecturer, Department of Commerce
Providence Women's College
Kozhikode, University of Calicut
e.mail ID: ninianoop@gmail.com

Abstract

Gold is considered as an important financial instrument now a days due to its unprecedented increase in price over the last seven or eight years. Irrespective of the fluctuating growth rate in the economy, gold continue to process a very unique position as an investment. People belong to different economic status are urged to buy or invest in gold. It is considered as a very useful asset to meet the unexpected financial requirements. Almost all the financial and non financial banking companies in the state of Kerala deal in gold pledging business. This paper attempt to identify the reasons behind choosing banking companies and non banking financial companies for availing gold loans and to compare the perception of customers of both the sector.

Key words: Attitude of officials, Gold loan, Interest rate, Perception of customers and Speed of services

Introduction

Financial institutions provide various types of financial services for its clients or members. Probably the most important financial service provided by financial institutions is acting as financial intermediaries. Banking company is a financial institution that accepts deposits and channels the money into lending activities. Non-bank financial companies (NBFCs) are financial institutions that provide banking services without meeting the legal definition of a bank i.e. one that does not hold a banking licence. Nonetheless, all operations of these institutions are still exercised under bank regulation. NBFCs offer most sorts of banking services, such as loans and credit facilities, private education funding, retirement planning, trading in money markets, underwriting stocks and shares, TFCs (Term Finance Certificate) and other obligations.

Theoretical background of the study

All the financial institutions both the banking and non banking are dealing with granting loans to their customers. They are providing different types of loan. But at present demand for gold loan is very high as compared to all other loans because the value of gold is increasing day by day and almost all customers have gold with them. It is more convenient for them to take loan with the

security of gold whenever needed. This paper aims to make a comparison between the gold loans provided by the banking companies and non banking financial companies. For this purpose State Bank of India was selected from Banking Companies and Muthoot Finance was selected from Non Banking Financial Companies. The main purpose of the study is to compare the customers' opinion about the services rendered with regard to gold loan facility provided by both the sector.

Statement of the problem

Both the banking and non banking companies are providing gold loans to their customers. But still no attempts had been made to know the customers opinion about the services provided by these two sectors with regard to the gold loan facility. It is highly relevant to know whether the services provided by these groups of institutions are similar or not. The time required for getting the service, the terms and conditions of service; especially as regards the rate of interest, speed with which the service is obtained, the attitude of the staff of the organisations etc. There is a need to know the customers responds, in this background the researchers make an attempt to assess and compare the response of customers about the gold loan facility provided by both category of institutions.

Scope of the study

The study mainly focuses only on the customers of State Bank of India from the Banking sector and Muthoot Finance from the Non Banking financial companies. Also it is limited to gold loan customers in the Calicut district.

Objectives the study

To assess and compare the customers responses about the gold loan schemes of banking and non banking financial companies.

Hypotheses

1. Ho: There is no significant difference in the income level of the customers taking gold loan from both the sector.
2. H0: There is no significant difference between the customers opinion with regard to interest rate charged by both the sectors.
3. H0: There is no significant difference between the opinions of customers of both the sector with regard to speed of services.

Methodology

The present study has been designed as a descriptive one based on primary data

Sample Design

For the purpose of conducting the study, State Bank of India was selected from the banking sector and Muthoot Finance from non banking financial companies. Samples of 60 customers were selected by following simple random technique. Among them 30 sample was taken from State Bank of India and 30 from Muthoot Finance.

Tools used for Data Collection

Field survey was conducted to collect primary data from the customers of both the banking and non banking financial companies. An interview schedule was developed for collecting data from the customers. A pilot survey was also carried out by selecting 5 customers

from each category institutions. On the basis of the experience of the pilot survey, necessary changes were made..

Tools for Data Analysis

For the purpose of data analysis different statistical and mathematical techniques were used and they are, Percentage Analysis, Chi square test, Kruskal Wallis test and Weighted average method

Limitations of the Study

As in the case of almost all social science research, this study is also not free from certain inherent limitations as to:

1. Study is originally based on the data supplied by the customers, its reliability influences the findings of the study
2. Only two institutions are selected for the study

Results and Discussions

The primary data collected were edited, tabulated and analysed and the results obtained are presented below.

Age Group

In order to identify the age group of the customers who availed gold loans from banking and non banking financial companies, the details are presented in the following table.

Table No. 1 Distribution of the age group of customers

Age Group	SBI		Muthoot Finance		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
20-30	2	6.67	0	0	2	3.33
30-40	15	50.00	18	60	33	55.00
40-50	12	40.00	8	26.67	20	33.33
50 & above	1	3.33	4	13.33	5	8.34
Total	30	100	30	100	60	100

Source: Primary data

As per the table it is clear that majority of the customers who avail gold loan from State Bank of India (50%) and Muthoot Finance (60%) belong to the age group of 30-40. And overall it was found that only very less customers (3.33%) of the age group 20-30 take gold loan from both the banks. It may be generalised that customers within the age group of 30 – 40 approach the institutions of gold loan purpose in comparison to other age groups.

Education

In order to know whether the qualification is an important factor which influences the customers to approach banking company or non banking company there is a need to collect the information about education of the customers. Necessary information was collected and is shown in the table 2.

Majority of the customers taking gold loan from State Bank of India are Graduates and those taking gold loan from Muthoot Finance are having tenth standard education. From this it can be revealed that education is an important factor which influences the customers to approach which sector.

Table No.2 Distribution based on Education of the customers

Education	SBI		Muthoot Finance		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
SSLC	5	16.67	13	43.33	18	30.00
Plus 2	3	10.00	9	30.00	12	20.00
Degree	12	40.00	5	16.67	17	28.33
PG	10	33.33	3	10.00	13	21.67
Total	30	100	30	100	60	100

Source: Primary data

Income Based

In order to identify which income group customers are taking gold loan from both the banking and non banking financial companies sufficient information are collected and is shown in the table below.

Table No.3 Distribution based on Income of customers

Income group (Rs.)	SBI		Muthoot Finance		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Below 10000	2	6.67	20	66.67	22	36.67
10000-20000	10	33.33	8	26.67	18	30.00
20000-30000	12	40.00	2	6.66	14	23.33
30000 & above	6	20.00	0	0	6	10.00
Total	30	100	30	100	60	100

Pearson Chi-square: 28.09, df=3, p value=.00000347

Source: Primary data

Majority of the customers taking gold loan from the State Bank of India (40 per cent) belong to the income group of 20000-30000 and that of Muthoot Finance (66.67 per cent) belong to the income group below 10000. And it is interesting to note that only 6.67 per cent customers having the income below 10000 are taking gold loan from State Bank of India.

In order to test whether there is any significant difference between the income group of the customers taking gold loan from both the banking and non banking financial companies the following hypothesis was formulated.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the income level of the customers taking gold loan from both the sector.

In order to test the hypothesis Chi square test was used. P value obtained at degrees of freedom 3 is .00000347 which is less than .05; the null hypothesis may be rejected. So it can be concluded that income of the customers is one of the important factors which determine the type of bank selected for availing gold loan.

Attitude and Approach of employees

Attitude and approach of the employees are very important in attracting the customers towards the institution. So in order to know the customers opinion about the employees of both the banking and non banking companies sufficient information are collected and is depicted in the table 4.

Table No. 4 Distribution of attitude and approaches of employees towards customers

Attitude and approach	SBI		Muthoot Finance		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
Very good	2	6.67	4	13.33	6	10.00
Good	8	26.66	15	50.00	23	38.33
Average	12	40	8	26.67	20	33.33
Bad	6	20	3	10.00	9	15.00
Very bad	2	6.67	0	0.00	2	03.34
Total	30	100	30	100	60	100.00

Source: *Primary data*

Majority of the customers of State Bank of India (40 per cent) opined that attitude and approach of the employees are only average. But in case of Muthoot Finance majority of the customers (50 per cent) opined that it is good. One notable point is that none of the customers of Muthoot Finance opined that attitude and approach of the employees are bad but 6.67 per cent customers of State Bank of India opined that it is very bad.

Interest Rate

Interest rate is an important factor that influences the customers to decide from which institutions to approach for gold loans. In order to identify the customers opinion about the interest rate of both the banking and non banking financial companies, the data collected are analysed by applying Kruskal Wallis test and the result shown in the table below.

Table No.5 Customers opinion about interest rate using Kruskal wallis test

	Median	N	Average rank	df	P value
SBI	3	30	40.75		
Muthoot Finance	2	30	20.25		
Total	3	60		1	0.00000108

Source: *Primary data*

As per the table median obtained for State Bank of India is 3 and that of Muthoot Finance is 2. Average rank of State Bank of India is 40.75 and Muthoot finance is 20.25. P value obtained at degrees of freedom 1 is .00000108.

In order to test whether there is any significant difference in the opinion of customers with regard to the interest rate following hypothesis was formulated

H₀: There is no significant difference between the customers opinion with regard to interest rate charged by both the sectors.

As the P value obtained .00000108 is less than .05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence it may be concluded that interest is an important factor which determines the selection of bank for gold loan transactions.

Speed of services

Most of the customers are spending their precious time for availing their service. In order to identify customers opinion about the speed of services rendered by both the sector sufficient information were collected and is shown in the table below.

Table No.6 Distribution of customers' opinion about the speed of service

Speed of service	SBI		Muthoot Finance		Total	
	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent	No.	Per cent
High	4	13.33	18	60.00	22	36.67
Medium	15	50.00	9	30.00	24	40.00
Low	11	36.67	3	10.00	14	23.33
Total	30	100.00	30	100.00	60	100.00

Pearson Chi-square: 14.98, df=2, pvalue=.0006

Source: Primary data

Majority of the customers of Muthoot finance (60 per cent) were of the opinion that speed of services is high but in case State Bank of India it was only medium. In order to test whether there is any difference in the opinion of customers of both the sector on the basis of speed of service rendered the following hypothesis was formulated.

H₀: There is no significant difference between the opinions of customers of both the sector with regard to speed of services.

As the p value obtained at degrees of freedom 2 is .0006 is less than .05, so the null hypothesis formulated is rejected i.e. speed of service is an influencing factor in the selection of bank for availing the gold loan.

Influencing factors

In order to identify the customers' opinion about the factors that influenced them to approach these financial institutions to take gold loan, sufficient information were collected. The customers were asked to rank these factors according to their preference and weights are assigned to each factor. Weighted average of each factors are shown in the table7.

Table No. 7: Distribution of weighted average of customers of State Bank of India based on the attracting factors

Factors	Total weight	Weighted average	Rank
Terms and conditions	246	4.47	3
Payment mode	180	3.27	5
Remittance mode	183	3.33	4
Interest rate	272	4.95	1
Availability	87	1.58	9
Customer service	96	1.75	7
easy processing	93	1.69	8
reputation of the bank	268	4.87	2
Locational Advantage	141	2.56	6
Personal contact with staff	84	1.53	10

Source: Primary data

In order to identify the factors that influenced the customers of State Bank of India to take gold loan from there, they were asked to rank according to their preference. Weights are assigned to each factor on the basis of the ranks given. Highest rank is given the weight ten, then nine given to next highest rank and so on. In this manner weights are assigned to each factor. Sum total of the weight of each factors are shown in the column, total weight. Weighted

average is obtained by dividing total weight by 55 (10+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1). The ranks are given on the basis of weighted average; the factor having highest weighted average is given the first rank and so on.

As per the table 7, first rank is given to the factor interest rate and second to the factor reputation of the bank, third to terms and conditions forth to remittance mode, fifth to payment mode, sixth to locational advantage, seven to customer service, eight to easy processing, nine to availability and ten to personal contact with staff.

Table No. 8: Distribution of weighted average of customers of Muthoot Finance based on the attracting factors

	Total weight	Weighted average	Rank
Terms and conditions	174	3.16	5
Payment mode	66	1.2	9
Remittance mode	90	1.64	8
Interest rate	57	1.04	10
Availability	252	4.58	1
Customer service	226	4.11	4
easy processing	240	4.36	2
reputation of the bank	153	2.78	7
Locational Advantage	162	2.98	6
Personal contact with staff	230	4.18	3

Source: Primary data

In order to identify the factors that influenced the customers of Muthoot Finance to take gold loan from there, they were asked to rank according to their preference. Weights are assigned to each factor on the basis of the ranks given. Highest rank is given the weight ten, then nine given to next highest rank and so on. In this manner weights are assigned to each factor. Sum total of the weight of each factors are shown in the column, total weight. Weighted average is obtained by dividing total weight by 55 (10+9+8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1). The ranks are given on the basis of weighted average; the factor having highest weighted average is given the first rank and so on.

As per the table 8, first rank is given to the factor availability, second to easy processing, third to personal contact with the staff, forth to customer service, fifth to terms and condition, sixth to location advantage, seven to reputation of the bank, eight to remittance mode, nine to payment mode and ten to interest rate.

Findings

On the basis of results obtained from the analysis, the major findings are as follows.

1. Most of the customers taking gold loan from both the banking and non banking financial companies belong to the age group of 30-40.
2. Qualification is also an important factor that influences the customers to decide from where to take gold loans.
3. Majority of the customers taking gold loans from the Banking sector belong to the income group of 20000-30000 but the customers who approach non banking sector for taking gold loans belong to the income group below 10000.

4. Attitude and approaches of employees of banking companies towards their customers was only average but in case of non banking companies it was good.
5. Opinion of the customers of both the banking and non banking is different with regard to the interest rate.
6. Speed of service rendered by banking sector is only medium but in case of non banking sector speed of service rendered is high.
7. The factors that attracted the customers to take gold loan from both the banking and non banking sector is entirely different. Interest rate, reputation of the bank and terms and conditions are the three important factors that attracted the customers of banking company. Availability, easy processing and personal contact with the staff are the three factors that influenced the customers of non banking financial companies.

Conclusion

This paper mainly focused on the customers' perception about gold loans schemes of both banking and non banking financial companies. Perception of the customers of both the sectors is entirely different. Mainly low income group customers prefer non banking sectors for taking gold loan. Main reason for that is availability and easy processing. Middle income and above level customers prefer banking companies for taking gold loans. The reason for this is interest rate and reputation of the bank. Overall the opinion of the customers of both the sectors is different.

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